

Using Local Culture to Teach Global Culture in Foreign Language Classrooms: A Case Study of EFL Students at Najran University

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Abstract

Teaching culture along or within foreign language teaching has won a wide currency in today's globalised world. However, there is no agreement on how to teach culture and which aspects of culture to teach. More importantly, the culture teaching materials at present in use have produced learners with an "us and them" worldview. These learners lack flexibility and are unable to accommodate the unpredictable realities of intercultural communication. Therefore, the need to develop new approaches that might increase the learners' understanding of others, to anticipate, to cope with misunderstanding and to decentre themselves is more than necessary. This paper proposes a reconsideration of the current methodologies with respect to the teaching of culture. It makes use of ethnographic techniques to teaching/learning culture that emphasize understanding of both the target and native culture(s). To cater for/to these concerns, the researchers designed a tailor-made intercultural syllabus in the form of classroom activities following ethnographic techniques methodology. A pre-post survey was used before and after the intervention was administered. The intervention was implemented with Saudi EFL students. The aim is twofold; to make the learners active analysts and interpreters of culture and to reflect on the learners' attitude towards people from what Kachru (1985) called the inner and outer circles. The results obtained showed that participants developed more positive views after the intervention compared to their views before the intervention.

Keywords: ethnography, intercultural awareness, intercultural communication, native culture, method, target culture

1. Introduction

In present day globalised world, learning a foreign language is synonymous with intercultural learning. This is because linguistic knowledge is not sufficient to develop intercultural competence. In addition, successful communication is not only about the acquisition of a linguistic code; it also involves knowledge about the culture of the target language. Brown (1994) explains the strong tie between language and culture as "intricately interwoven so that one cannot separate the two without losing the significance of either language or culture" (p. 165).

Regarding the significance of teaching culture besides teaching the four skills, Tomalin (2008) argues that culture should be taught as a fifth skill because of the worldwide dominance of the English language and globalisation. He points out that teaching culture equips learners with mindset and techniques required to adjust the use of English language with other culture (2008).

Gao (2006) asserts that language learning entails culture learning and subsequently language teaching entails cultural teaching (p. 59). However, the often-raised question is whether this knowledge about the foreign culture is sufficient to meet intercultural objectives. More importantly, if it does, how should a foreign language teacher approach it? To answer this question, Gao (2006) emphasizes that foreign language teacher should raise students' cultural awareness as well as help them to improve their communication competence. In addition, Sowden (2007) insists that in the classroom, language teachers should take into consideration not only students' culture but also their own culture (p. 305).

The difficulty or unwillingness in dealing with culture relates to the complexity of the term culture itself. Like language, culture is dynamic and constantly changing (Nieto, 2000); hence, the existence of a myriad of

definitions of culture. A review of literature about culture shows that culture is seen from either a humanistic or a social perspective. The former views culture as general knowledge of history, literature, and the material productions of a particular social group; the latter relates culture to the native speakers' "attitudes and beliefs, ways of thinking, behaving and remembering" (Nostrand, 1989, p. 51). These views about culture are reflected in the various approaches to teaching culture. A close examination of these approaches reveals that the topics most often dealt with relate to either history, geography, literature and arts, or beliefs, values, customs or behaviours. They consider the native speaker a feasible, realistic or appropriate model and tend to view the learners as incomplete native speakers. The result is a neglect of the learner's culture and communication styles (Byram, 1997) despite the fact that "the processes operating when we communicate interculturally are the same as when we communicate intraculturally" (Gudykunst, 1994). These facts-oriented approaches have done little, if at all, to develop the learners' intercultural awareness. They have often developed stereotypes in the learners (Byram & Feng, 2005); they were often described as damaging and have produced learners with an "us and them" worldview. Therefore, in Byram's words, "learners need to see their role not as imitators of native speakers but as social actors engaging with other social actors in a particular kind of communication and interaction which is different from that between native speakers." (1997, p. 21). Hence, a change in orientation from approaches that focus on a country as a single representative of a language and culture to an approach that considers the diversity of culture, be it the target culture or the learner's culture, if necessary.

2. Previous Literature on English as an International Language and Intercultural Awareness

Given the fact that English as an international language is a daily encounter for millions of people "who do not speak the same first language" (Kirkpatrick, 2007, p. 155), one can safely say that, in addition to being the language of wider communication, English also serves to gain access to different scientific resources. More importantly, about 1.5 billion people, excluding native speakers, speak English (Graddol, 1997). These people, as asserted by Kachru (2005), do not necessarily learn English to communicate with native speakers, but probably with speakers with no English cultural background.

In her tripartite model of world Englishes, Kachru (1985) described the changing distribution and functions of English worldwide and classified them into the inner circle, the outer circle and the expanding circle. The inner circle encompasses the contexts where English is spoken by natives such as the UK and the US. The outer circle refers to countries where English is used as a second language like India and Nigeria. The expanding circle includes countries where English is used as a foreign language like Saudi Arabia and Japan. According to Kachru, "English has multicultural identities" (1985, p. 357) with equal status for all varieties.

Following the above line of thought, English, as an international language, no longer relates to one single country and "cannot be linked to any one country or culture; rather it must belong to those who use it" (McKay, 2002, p. 1) because it represents "the contextual experiences of those who use it" (Kachru & Nelson, 2006, p. 16). Consequently, learning about cultures of what Kachru (1985) terms Inner Circle countries is now challenged. This change in orientation has made the job of teachers of English as a foreign language more difficult. Teachers will have to decide as to which country's culture to integrate in their syllabi. In the past, most English as a foreign language syllabus took either Britain or the US as their main reference for cultural information. Now, "the teaching and learning of an international language must be based on an entirely different set of assumptions" (McKay, 2002, p. 1). Teaching English as a foreign language must expand its syllabus to include cultures from countries outside the inner circle. One possible solution to the above situation is to move from emphasis on cultural awareness to intercultural awareness.

Cultural awareness and intercultural awareness refer to the understanding of the role culture plays in communication. In the words of Baker (2015), "Cultural awareness focuses on national cultures and intercultural awareness on more dynamic and flexible relationships between languages and cultures" (p. 135). Simply put, cultural awareness refers to knowledge and understanding of the ways culture influences one's and others' beliefs, attitudes, behaviours, perceptions and ways of communication. It involves awareness of one's own and others' culturally based behaviour and the ability to explain one's cultural stance. In the words of Tomalin and Stempleski (1993), cultural awareness calls for "sensitivity to the impact of culturally-induced behaviour on language use and communication".

Byram (1997) gives another more comprehensive definition of cultural awareness. For him, cultural awareness comprises five *savoirs* namely,

- *Savoirs*: knowledge of self and others, of interaction, of social groups and their products and practices;
- *Savoir être*: intercultural attitudes such as openness, willingness to relativize one's own values, beliefs and behaviours and value those of others;

- Savoir comprendre: skills of interpreting and relating such as the ability to interpret an event from another culture and relate it to events from one's own;
- Savoir apprendre/faire: skills of discovery and/or interaction such as the ability to acquire new knowledge of cultures and cultural practices and also use it in interaction;
- Savoir s'engager: critical cultural awareness which implies the ability to critically evaluate perspectives, practices and products in both one's own and other cultures.

Following this line of reasoning, the development of cultural awareness results from one's knowledge of culturally based behaviour and values. However, limiting this knowledge to the American and British cultures because of their dominance does not, according to Risager (1991), do justice to the many international contexts where English is used and where the norms of communication differ sharply from those in the American and British culture. In addition, the acquisition of this knowledge does not necessarily lead to a change in prejudiced attitudes (Kramersch, 1993).

However, intercultural awareness refers to the knowledge and skills, be they linguistic or cultural, which enable one to communicate successfully in different sociocultural contexts. It involves an understanding of how cultures and culturally determined differences affect communication in today's globalised world (Schaules, 2007). This knowledge should not be the end product of foreign language teaching; the ultimate outcome is intercultural speakers (Byram & Zarate, 1997) who possess skills of tolerance, interpretation and comparison of cultural practices which enable them "to understand foreign attitudes, values, and mindsets" (Kramersch, 1996 p. 23). In brief, Intercultural awareness implies a move from 'ethnocentrism' to 'ethno-relativism', the ability to 'decentre', to see things from someone else's perspective, to develop 'empathy' as well as an awareness of the intercultural process of change of both individuals and societies arising out of the dynamics of encounters between them (Rantz & Horan, 2005, p. 211). As such, intercultural awareness refers to a conscious understanding of the role culture can have in intercultural encounters.

3. The Current Study

One possible way to cater for the above-mentioned concern is the use of ethnographic techniques to raise the learners' awareness of the target language culture. Ethnography, as defined in the literature, is "the work of describing a culture" the aim of which is "to understand another way of life from the native point of view (Spradley, 1979, p. 3). The use of ethnography in foreign language teaching is well documented in the literature (Byram, 1997) and (Roberts, 1993). However, the reader is warned that the use of ethnography is meant to develop a teaching methodology rather than to carry ethnographic research about the teaching environments or language use outside the classroom. Resort to this type of methodology is motivated by the lingua franca status of English. Today, the English language is no longer under the jurisdiction of native speakers. It is spoken in many different varieties each of which has its own culture. Therefore, to copy the native speakers is of limited use. Today's learners of English need to develop skills that enable them to communicate in intercultural encounters, to develop their own worldview, to see differences as a resource and to interpret personal and social experiences (Sellami, 2000).

"Learning from observation" rather than "describing people" is the motto for the ethnographic approach to teaching culture to raise the learners' intercultural awareness as part of intercultural communicative competence. One guiding principle of this approach is to develop in the learner skills of accommodation, negotiation, mediation and flexibility, and knowledge of other cultures and communicative systems. These skills are their only boarding pass to see the foreign language and culture from both the "emic and etic perspectives". However, the often-raised question is how ethnographic research techniques can be reproduced in classrooms situated in non-native language environments for practicing ethnographic skills in order to develop the learners' intercultural awareness. To go from theorising to classroom practice in the teaching of culture to raise the learners' intercultural awareness, the following scheme is suggested.

4. Research Study Design

This research aims to help Saudi learners of English at Najran University based in Saudi Arabia surpass the traditional knowledge-oriented teaching approaches and methods at present in use which, hopefully, would enable them to go beyond the inner-circle cultural content and give them room to engage in deep levels of reflection. More to the point, given the fact that English (as a foreign language) teaching practices in Saudi Arabia should go beyond the native speakers' culture to include the local culture, an appropriate pedagogy that favours the learners' voice and experience, and contextual learning in the form of ethnographic techniques needs to be framed. The design of this study, therefore, took these factors into consideration and proposed two steps.

The first step was to enable the participants to practice ethnographic skills to develop learners' intercultural awareness and second to enrol them in the ethnographic interviewing techniques.

4.1 Participants and Procedure

The sample of this study consists of thirty-two male fourth and fifth level students in the English and translation departments at Najran University. All of them were native speakers of Arabic, most of them were from Najran and few were from other regions.

At baseline and after 45 hours of follow-up the participants completed a demographic survey (adapted from Robinson-Stuart & Nocon, 1996) (see Appendix A). The aim was to get some insights into the learners' ability to explore the diversity and complexity of their own local and national cultural groupings and their understanding of the culture of English-speaking people.

4.2 The Intervention

In order to have the above-mentioned ethnographic approach implemented, hopefully in an efficient way, to concretize the set of assumptions it embraces and to see what impact it might have on the learners, an experiment was conducted. To this end, the thirty-two participants were randomly assigned to the treatment (experimental) versus the control groups. The experiment consists of assigning participants in the experimental group to treatment, and care was taken to ensure that any differences observed between subjects in both groups must be caused by the treatment itself.

Based on the premises of the ethnographic approach, a tailor-made intercultural syllabus was developed. Examples of the implemented intervention are classroom activities and interviews (See Appendix B). The aim is to make the learners active analysts and interpreters of culture which ultimately would promote their intercultural awareness while also decentring themselves from both the native and target cultures. The other aim the intervention seeks to reach was a reflection on the learners' attitude towards people from what Kachru (1985) called the inner and outer circles. The intervention was implemented with Saudi learners training to become EFL teachers in different secondary schools in Saudi Arabia.

The implementation of such ethnographic techniques as interviewing, observation and interpretation using the above-mentioned activities was carried out by one of the English Department staff members. Prior to the treatment phase, a pre-test was given to both groups. The test is in the form of a story (See Appendix C) (adapted from Hofstede et al., 2002) and the participants were asked to determine which words and phrases indicate cultural differences, identify the cultural concept(s), analyse the situation, and provide the contextual meaning.

The treatment lasted for fourteen weeks (three hours a week) during the first semester of the academic year 2019/2020. The learners were first trained to observe and interpret the different situations they were presented with. The aim is to identify the effects of cultural conditioning on their own perceptual lens. Their responses to different situations were elicited both in writing and orally. Only towards the end of their training were they initiated to ethnographic interviewing techniques. The ethnographic interviewing techniques were used in this study because it was believed they could help explore cultural similarities and differences in any context (Robinson-Stuart & Nocon, 1996) (It should be noted at this point that conducting face-to-face interviews with native speakers was almost not an option in Najran. Therefore, participants were encouraged to conduct their interviews with native speakers via on-line programs. Students were urged to conduct three to four interviews with native speakers of English). To make the interviews more focused on culture, students were instructed to concentrate on both the interviewees' culture as well as their own. Multilevel analyses were used to test the effectiveness of the activities.

After the intervention, a posttest was administered to both groups to examine the impact of the treatment. Like in the pretest, the participants were presented with a culturally loaded story (See Appendix D) (adapted from Hofstede et al., 2002) and were required to determine which words and phrases indicate cultural differences, identify the cultural concept(s), analyse the situation, and provide the contextual meaning.

4.3 Results

Previous studies found that there was a positive effect on student's attitudes after participating in ethnographic interviewing of target language speakers (Robinson-Stuart & Nocon, 1996; Roberts et al., 2001; Bateman, 2003). This study aims to achieve the same conclusion. The attitude surveys were analysed using frequency distribution of responses to Likert-style questions.

The first question in the survey relates to the reasons behind the students' choice to study English at the university (See Figure 1). Fifty-five percent (55%) of the students answered "others" and reported that their

choice was due to their low GPA, English major was the only option. Studying English was a personal interest to 30% of the students. The least percentage (15%) goes to students who decided to study English because of their family pressure.

Figure 1. Why did you choose to study English at university?

As illustrated in Figure 2 below, students' answers vary in response to the second question which enquires into their need to learn English. Correlating the students' answers to question items one and two, one notices that almost the same percentage who answered "others" selected the first option *job prospects*; thirty five percent (35%) believe they need English as a personal enrichment. The rest of the answers go to *interest in travel*.

Figure 2. How would you describe your need to learn English?

The third question is about the goal behind studying English. Most students opted for 'get a better job' as an answer. The rest of the students' answers are almost divided between 'requirement' and 'other' (See Figure 3).

Figure 3. How would describe your goal in your study of English?

The fourth question relates to the number of native speakers' friends the participants may have. Of the total number of the participants, only three of them have native speakers' friends.

Regarding the correlation between the pre and post surveys, it is worth discussing some statistical remarks on pre and post-test questions. The paired t-test statistical analysis showed that there is no significant difference between the pre-intervention survey ($M = 5.1$) and the post-intervention survey ($M = 5.6$) ($t = -1.5066$, $df = 4$, $p = 0.2064$).

In fact, the reason why p-value is not significant above is due to the small number of questions (5 questions). So, it is suggested that the result be instead interpreted based on the mean difference. The post-intervention mean is higher than that of the pre-intervention which indicates that the participants show more positive views after the intervention compared to their views before the intervention.

4.4 Analysis of the Experiment Results

4.4.1 Control Group Pretest and Posttest Results

The results obtained from the pretest and the posttest of the control group are displayed in the tables below.

Table 1. Control group pre-test scores

Participants	Pre-test scores	Participants	Pre-test scores
Participant 01	09.5	Participant 09	09.5
Participant 02	08.5	Participant 10	11
Participant 03	09	Participant 11	13
Participant 04	09	Participant 12	10.5
Participant 05	10	Participant 13	07
Participant 06	10.5	Participant 14	04.5
Participant 07	10	Participant 15	15.5
Participant 08	09	Participant 16	11

Table 2. Control group post-test scores

Participants	Post-test scores	Participants	Post-test scores
Participant 01	10.5	Participant 09	12.5
Participant 02	09	Participant 10	11.5
Participant 03	10.5	Participant 11	12.5
Participant 04	15	Participant 12	12
Participant 05	09	Participant 13	09
Participant 06	08	Participant 14	09
Participant 07	11	Participant 15	14
Participant 08	10.5	Participant 16	11.5

Table 3. Control group gain scores

Participants	Pre-test scores	Post-test scores	Gain scores
Participants 01	09.5	10.5	+1
Participants 02	08.5	09	+1
Participants 03	09	10.5	+1.5
Participant 04	09	15	+6
Participant 05	10	09	+1
Participant 06	10.5	08	-2.5
Participant 07	10	11	+1
Participant 08	09	10.5	+1.5
Participant 09	09.5	12.5	+3
Participant 10	11	11.5	+0.5
Participant 11	13	12.5	-1.5
Participant 12	10.5	12	+1.5
Participant 13	07	09	+2
Participant 14	04.5	09	+4.5
Participant 15	15.5	14	-1.5
Participant 16	10	11.5	+1.5

4.4.2 Experimental Group Pre-test and Post-test Results

The results obtained from the experimental group are displayed in the following tables.

Table 4. Experimental group pre-test scores

Participants	Post-test scores	Participants	Post-test scores
Participant 01	10	Participant 09	14.5
Participant 02	09.5	Participant 10	06.5
Participant 03	09	Participant 11	08
Participant 04	08	Participant 12	11.5
Participant 05	14	Participant 13	10.5
Participant 06	10.5	Participant 14	06.5
Participant 07	09.5	Participant 15	13
Participant 08	05	Participant 16	10

Table 5. Experimental group post-test scores

Participants	Post-test scores	Participants	Post-test scores
Participant 01	13	Participant 09	13.5
Participant 02	15.5	Participant 10	13
Participant 03	17	Participant 11	15
Participant 04	11	Participant 12	15
Participant 05	14	Participant 13	15.5
Participant 06	14	Participant 14	15.5
Participant 07	13	Participant 15	12
Participant 08	09.5	Participant 16	14

Table 6. Experimental group gain scores

Participants	Pre-test scores	Post-test scores	Gain scores
Participant 01	10	13	+3
Participant 02	09.5	15.5	+6
Participant 03	09	12	+3
Participant 04	08	11	+3
Participant 05	14	14	/
Participant 06	10.5	14	+3,5
Participant 07	09.5	13	+3,5
Participant 08	05	09.5	+4,5
Participant 09	14.5	13.5	-1
Participant 10	06.5	13	+6,5
Participant 11	08	15	+7
Participant 12	11.5	15	+3,5
Participant 13	10.5	15.5	+5
Participant 14	06.5	15.5	+9
Participant 15	13	12	-1
Participant 16	10	14	+4

To make sure that the two groups of participants recruited for this study have the same level with regard to their culture observational and analytical skills, an independent t-test was administered as an independent variable and their score on the pre-test only as of the dependent variable. The results show no significant difference between the two groups' scores in the pre-test ($t(1,30) = 0.07, p > 0.1$). This leads one to conclude that there is no major difference between the two groups prior to conducting this study.

The data were analysed with a two-way mixed ANOVA; with groups (Control vs. Experimental) as the between-subject variable whereas the Test Type (Pre vs. Post) as the within-subject variable. The results show that there is a significant main effect of Test Type in that a higher score is observed in the post-test (mean = 12.2) compared to the pre-test (mean = 9.8), ($F(1,30) = 30.9, p < 0.001$) and the main effect of Group almost reaches ($F(1,30) = 30.9, p = 0.07$). However, there is a significant interaction between Group and Test Type ($F(1,30) = 8.9, p < 0.006$) indicating that the main effect of Test type may differ based on which group of participants. Thus, a post hoc multiple comparisons was conducted for each group of participants separately.

The post hoc results of the control group show a non-significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the pre-test score (mean = 9.84) and the post-test score (mean = 10.97). On the other hand, a significantly higher score ($p < 0.001$) is observed in the post-test (mean = 13.74) compared to the pre-test (mean = 9.75) of the Experimental group indicating a significant effect of the intervention implanted in this study on the participants' learning outcome.

Figure 4. A bar graph comparing the mean scores of both groups on each test type

As shown by the results displayed in the tables above, there are obvious differences between the experimental and control groups with regard to the performance of each in the pre-test and the post-test. These differences are attributable to the fact that the use of ethnographic techniques enabled the learners in the experimental group to articulate and reflect upon their native culture and the foreign language culture. These techniques also helped them gain cultural capital that enables them to understand both cultures. How well this cultural understanding is gained depends on the approach and activities implemented in the intervention.

5. Conclusion

The basic demographic profile of the participants enabled the researchers to explore the participants' attitude towards English which in turn helped them develop appropriate teaching strategies for the treatment phase. These strategies are meant to change the participants' negative attitude towards learning English or for that matter to avoid the development of negative attitudes towards the English language. This is motivated by the participants' answers to question one (See p. 43 above) to which 55% of the participants believed that their low GPA did not allow them to choose other subjects to study than English. Consequently, they felt as if they were learning it as a compulsory subject. Such a negative belief may lead to class anxiety and negative attitudes.

In addition, the ethnographic approach of the type discussed above is a good starting point for both teachers and learners to develop intercultural awareness. It will develop in the learners an awareness of sociocultural and sociolinguistic differences that might exist between their first language culture and the target language culture. It provides them with tools, knowledge and skills necessary to become intercultural speakers. The suggested methodology favours learner centred activities, group and pair work and involves the learners in both oral and

written work. It is a pattern based rather than fact-based methodology. It goes beyond the informational role of teaching of culture. Its main aim is the development of an ethnographic perspective within the learners rather than automatic imitation. That is, to make the learners active analysts and interpreters of culture.

More to the point, the results indicate that the intervention had a significant and positive impact on the observational and interpretive skills of the participants in the experimental group. The ethnographic techniques of the type suggested in the cultural syllabus helped the participants in the experimental group understand cultural happenstances, reflect on their own culture, talk about the target culture, articulate cultural differences, understand the target culture and its meaning making possibilities through the process of discovery stipulated by the ethnographic techniques. Thus, the methodological orientation proclaimed in this paper seems sound and well grounded.

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Appendix A

Pre-Post Survey

Part A: Please provide the following information:

- 1) Gender: Male/ Female
- 2) Number of years living in an English-speaking country:
- 3) In your opinion, what is the level of your English? (Circle one)

Minimal	Poor	Fair	Good	Very good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5	6

Part B

I. Please answer each of the following questions by writing in the space provided the number of the answer which best describes your case:

- 1) Why did you choose to study English?
- a) Prerequisite

- b) Family Pressure
 - c) Personal Interest
 - d) Fun
 - e) Other (Describe)
- 2) How would you describe your need to learn English? (you may use more than one.)
- a) Requirement
 - b) Personal enrichment
 - c) Interest in culture
 - d) interest in English people
 - e) Interest in travel
 - f) Job prospects
 - g) Other (Describe)
- 3) How would describe your goal in your study of English?
- a) Requirement
 - b) Get a better job
 - c) Learn more about other people and cultures.
 - d) Other (Describe)
- 4) Do you have English/American (any native speakers of English) friends?
- a) (0)
 - b) (1-5)
 - c) (3-5)
 - d) (10+)

II. Please answer the following items by circling the number which most reflects your feeling about the following statements. The numbers correspond to the following scale:

Disagree strongly	Disagree moderately	Disagree slightly	Agree slightly	Agree moderately	Agree strongly
1	2	3	4	5	6

1. English will help me make more English-speaking friends.
2. English will help me make more English friends.
3. A language requirement exposes students to a necessary subject.
4. Knowing English will allow me to help others who are not as lucky as I am.
5. Knowing English will increase my income potential.

Appendix B

Activities and Methodology Used during the Intervention

Phase one

One possible way to aid the learners to practice ethnographic skills is through teaching them ethnographic techniques (Byram & Fleming, 1998) such as interviewing, observation, and journals. This type of teaching revolves mainly around the subject matter of ethnographic research, how it is carried out, how conclusions are drawn, and how results are interpreted. More importantly, the learners should understand that as ethnographers their role is not to study people but to learn from them in order to better understand how they perceive others, themselves, and social differences (Spradley, 1979). If time permits, teachers can devote one or two class sessions to lecture the learners on ethnography before embarking on doing ethnographic research.

Phase Two

Teaching culture geared toward the development of intercultural awareness and understanding is to make of the

learner's culture part of the curriculum content (Byram & Feng, 2005). The aim is to lead the learners to understand their perspectives and to reflect on their own culture in order to relativize their often taken for granted views of themselves and their culture (Byram et al., 1994). The main impetus for such a methodological orientation is that learners cannot learn about values of another culture without considering those of their own. Consequently, the use of an ethnographic methodology will "lead students to some understanding of the notion of culturally determined behaviour" (Fantini, 1997, p. 167). Following the same line of reasoning, Damen (1987) believes that awareness of self is a step forward towards awareness of others. He wrote, "Cross-cultural awareness involves uncovering and understanding one's own culturally conditioned behaviour and thinking, as well as the patterns of others. Thus, the process involves not only perceiving the similarities and differences in other cultures but also recognizing the givens of the native culture" (p. 141). Hence, to enable them to develop self-awareness and self-reflectiveness, the learners will practice self-directed ethnography both inside and outside classrooms. In the course of their ethnographic research, the learners will have to explore each other's backgrounds, memberships, interests, perspectives and identities. This can be done inside the classrooms or outside in their communities and social circles. Using ethnographic techniques enables the learners to have a better understanding of themselves as cultural beings, of the subcultures within their national culture, and most important of all, understanding of cultural similarities and shared values as well as differences. In terms of classroom practice, the following steps may help in doing a mini-project on a particular native culture aspect in the learners' community. (Adapted from Spradley, 1980).

- a. Problem Identification: Learners are invited to observe some cultural aspects, something they do not understand or would like to know more about.
- b. Hypothesis Formulation: Learners write down some questions and then formulate a hypothesis.
- c. Explanation/Interpretation: Learners try to identify the causes, reasons, or explanations for what they have observed in order to prove/test whether their hypothesis is true or false.

After explaining the above scheme, the teacher may remind the learners that doing ethnographic research is something people always do either consciously or unconsciously. Whenever someone finds himself in a new situation, the obvious thing she/he does is to observe the situation, the people, their behaviour...etc.

Depending on the learners' needs and interests, the teacher, together with the students, may agree on a cultural theme to deal with. Suppose they agree to work on the following theme: "Different age groups use computers differently". Depending on class size, the teacher divides the class into groups of two or three. During class time, the learners, with the help of the teacher, write questions, formulate hypotheses, and choose the method (interview or survey) to follow in investigating the theme. The rest of the work is to be completed as homework. Outside the classroom, the learners will survey/interview people in order to identify the reasons and find explanations for computer use differences among different age groups in order to test their hypotheses. The next day in class, they will have to make a formal report and presentation of their experience and results. Following this activity, the learners will be exposed to local differences and diversities at home which may help them develop cultural awareness as a precursor to intercultural awareness.

Phase three

Now that the learners have come to understand how their native culture influences their own behaviour and communicative practices, the next phase is to explore the target language culture using ethnographic techniques. To aid the learners, the following activity and the steps necessary in its implementation are explained.

Activity: We See What We Want to See (Awareness, Knowledge)

Goal: to help learners avoid bringing their own cultural frame of interpretation to any situation.

Procedure: Students are presented with a picture. They look at the picture briefly and write down what they think it might show. A discussion of different interpretations given by the learners follows. During the discussion, the learners try to figure out what attributes (family relationships, gender and age difference, professional or religious roles) influenced their interpretation. At the end, a set of interpretations made by people from other parts of the world is handed to the learners to find out how they interpreted the image.

Rationale: The aim of this activity is to make the learners aware of the fact that just by looking at a situation, one cannot tell what is happening. Unconsciously, people bring their own cultural frame of interpretation to any situation. This is not to say that culture alone determines how one interprets a picture or a situation. One's own unique history and personality also play an important role.

Materials: The materials for this activity consist of a set of images large enough to be presented as a slideshow

and a set of possible interpretations made by people from different international cultural background and with different age ranges.

Lesson from this activity: Often one's culture influences how one perceives and interprets reality, consequently her/his interpretation and understanding may not be accurate. Bringing one's own cultural frame of interpretation to any situation may result in ethnocentrism, prejudice, stereotypes, racism, and discrimination.

Possible interpretations:

- Two women are walking and a man threatens one of the women with a piece of wood
- Two men are attacking a woman
- A woman steps aside to let a blind man pass
- A beggar and a woman
- Gardening
- A farm family working on their land
- Two people helping each other do something
- Poor people. The man is digging for something and the woman is waiting to take it
- A man is digging a hole and a woman is dropping seeds in it
- A man cleaning the floor (Adapted from Hofstede, 2002).

This activity may be used to train students to develop observational skills and to understand that differences may be found between members of a single social group or between social groups themselves. Despite the fact that this type of image is easy to interpret, still the learners may wonder why their ways of seeing the image are different from both that of their peers and that of other people from other parts of the world (Note that people who gave their interpretation of the same image came from Bolivia, China, France, Indonesia, Italy, the Netherlands, Peru, Tunisia, and Uganda). This might enable the learners to understand differences within and between cultures and to reflect on differences in perceptions, prejudices and attitudes. In addition, teaching culture according to this activity involves cultures, in Kachru's terms (1985), from the expanding circle.

Appendix C

Instructions: Read the story below and underline the culturally significant words or phrases, determine which words and phrases indicate cultural differences, identify the cultural concept(s), analyse the situation, and provide the contextual meaning.

The Wedding Guest

An American was hired as an external consultant to assess the progress of a development project in Asia. The consultant already suspected from other sources that the project was in trouble due to mismanagement by the Northern European project leader. This opinion was confirmed to him by an Asian engineer, albeit in a reluctant manner. From the Asian's veiled account, the consultant deduced that the project leader was in fact an utter failure. The consultant then asked the Asian whether he had told the project leader that he was not doing well. "That is not so," said the Asian. "Why not?" asked the consultant. The Asian engineer replied, "He was a guest at my wedding."

Appendix D

Instructions: Read the story below and underline the culturally significant words or phrases, determine which words and phrases indicate cultural differences, identify the cultural concept(s), analyse the situation, and provide the contextual meaning.

Adam and the Napkin

Two years ago, I lived with an Irish family for fifteen days during the summer. The first day when I sat at the table to have lunch, I realized that there was no napkin beside my plate. I asked the Irishwoman for one, and she reacted as if I had asked for the strangest thing in the world. I felt bad because I thought that they thought I was a dirty boy who needed a napkin to clean what I was going to soil. However, I was sure that my behaviour was correct. Afterward, she took a napkin and gave it to me, and for the remaining days she did the same not only for me but also for the rest of the family.

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